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**LINGUISTIC AND SPEECH MEANS OF EXPRESSING NEGATION
IN ENGLISH AND UKRAINIAN OFFICIAL AND BUSINESS DISCOURSE**

This article suggests a new approach to the negation study in English and Ukrainian official and business communication as cognitive and discursive formation. Thus, the means of expressing objections in the official-business discourse in the English and Ukrainian languages and the relation of the category of objection to linguistic universals. With the help of a historical comparative research method, general cultural trends in the field of official and business communication between English and Ukrainian speakers were identified. General cultural tendencies in the sphere of English and Ukrainian speakers' official and business communication were determined. The methods of linguistic and speech means of negation comparison in English and Ukrainian official and business discourse were devised. Conclusions: the list of linguistic means on English and Ukrainian different system levels concerning to the possibility of the negative meaning realization in business discourse were determined.

Key words: cognitive and discursive formation, linguistic means, speech means, negation, official and business discourse, frame model.

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Лінгвістичні та мовні засоби вираження заперечення в англійському та українському офіційному та діловому дискурсі

Ця стаття пропонує новий підхід до вивчення заперечення в англійському та українському офіційному та діловому спілкуванні як когнітивне та дискурсивне формування. Отже, мета статті – дослідження засобів вираження заперечення в офіційно-діловому дискурсі в англійській та українській мовах та відношення категорії заперечення до лінгвістичних універсалій. За допомогою історично-порівняльного методу дослідження було визначено загальні культурні тенденції у сфері офіційного та ділового спілкування англійських та українських ораторів. Розроблено методи порівняння мовних та мовленнєвих засобів заперечення в англійському та українському офіційному та діловому дискурсі. Визначено перелік

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лінгвістичних засобів на різних рівнях англійської та української мов стосовно можливості реалізації негативного значення в діловому дискурсі.

Ключові слова: пізнавальна та дискурсивна формація, лінгвістичні засоби, мовні засоби, заперечення, офіційний та діловий дискурс, рамкова модель.

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Лингвистические и языковые средства выражения отрицания в английском и украинском официальном и деловом дискурсе

Эта статья предлагает новый подход к изучению отрицания в английском и украинском официальном и деловом общении как когнитивное и дискурсивное формирования. Итак, цель статьи – исследование способов выражения отрицания в официально-деловом дискурсе в английском и украинском языках и отношение категории отрицания к лингвистическим универсалиям. С помощью историко-сравнительного метода исследования, были определены общие культурные тенденции в сфере официального и делового общения английских и украинских ораторов. Разработаны методы сравнения языковых и речевых средств отрицания в английском и украинском официальном и деловом дискурсе. Определен перечень лингвистических средств на различных уровнях английского и украинского языков относительно возможности реализации отрицательного значения в деловом дискурсе.

Ключевые слова: познавательная и дискурсивная формація, лингвистические средства, языковые средства.

Introduction. Negation is a form of human thought, which confirms the high level of his consciousness to comprehend the phenomena of life, is one of the most important categories of language, without the use of which is now impossible to imagine the full human communication in any language.

The previous studies and analyses. Ontological value and functional activity categories of objections, which is reflected in the systems of all natural languages, gives researchers reason to refer the objection to linguistic universals (L. Barkhudarov, V. Bondarenko, A. Vezhbytskaya, O. Jespersen, A. Paslavskiy, V. Yartseva, etc.) such as functional-semantic formations has been caused by human desire for differentiation (first and by negation) phenomena of life and a reflection of this process in the language.

As a universal language category with complex and multidimensional semantics and diversified arsenal of means of expression, denial in every new area of linguistics becomes every other interpretation. In this regard, today in linguistics observed treatment categories in psychological denial (Bulakh, 1957); logical and grammatical (Shendels, 1979) aspects.

The complexity of the system means of expression and semantic heterogeneity objection as linguistic universals (Shendels, 1979) updates its interpretation in the light of cognitive-discursive approach, because different types of discourses objection is realized by means of speech means that no negative-language semantics. The problem is compounded when it comes to official business discourse, which is traditionally defined as clearly regulated in terms of its composite structure and established a set of linguistic resources.

The purpose of the article is to study the means of expressing objections in the official-business discourse in the English and Ukrainian languages and the relation of the category of objection to linguistic universals.

The main plot of the article. The relevance of the research caused anthropocentric orientation in modern linguistic works on the study of language and society the relationships, on the one hand, and the communication strategies of business interaction of different societies that ensure the effectiveness of cross-cultural contacts – on the other. Comprehensive analysis of the cognitive-discursive mechanisms of objectification objection to the official-business communication is necessary for determining how common patterns of language means that different structural language used to express objections and differences of ethnic in speech means that actualize a negative semantics for rejecting or adjusting business ideas partner.

Category negation is commonly represented in languages at the morphological and lexical and syntactic levels. This raises questions about the principles of classification objections. Typically, the objections are classified in terms of syntactic functions in the sentence. The most common objection is syntactic classification based on categories of formal logic Kant, according to which the denial of language is divided into two types:

- 1) qualitative objections;
- 2) quantitative negation (Bessonova, 2002).

Instead, this classification is not correct, because, in our opinion, the difference between denial and verbal noun can be defined as opposed to quantitative and qualitative categories. In addition, A. Jespersen opposes the division of objections to the quantitative and qualitative facts pointing to the discrepancy history of the language, while still inclined to understand the objection as a quantitative category (Jespersen, 1964, p. 67).

Syntax classification O Jespersen is not associated with morphological. By O. Jespersen, verbal objections generally not included in the classification of objections, expressed as a negative prefix and suffix. So, verbal objections scientist classifies separately (Jespersen, 1964, p. 79).

Among nouns and adjectives with negative evaluative semantics, it is necessary to distinguish lexical units, which call negative feelings and emotions that feel the speaker in relation to the recipient: English *contemptible*, *despicable*, *disgusting*, *revolting*, *unpleasant*, *detestable*, *hateful*; as well as lexical units implementing any deviation from the norm in the direction of a negative assessment of the identity of the addressee:

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English *lazy, tactless, brutish, bitter, mean, plain, inhuman, nasty, infamous, rude, ugly, insignificant, snotty, hopeless, foolish, cruel, stubborn, selfish, stupid, vain, boring, unimportant, vile*. Negative evaluation is closely intertwined with expressiveness and is its integral component, along with emotional, logical enhancement and imagery. Expressive loaded model as any of the sign, sold in speech, emotional function of this model revealed by filling lexical analysis of content and contextual environment. Understanding expressiveness as a structural reaction of syntax to the presence of emotions or a different degree of their discovery involves the study of expressiveness at the syntactic level. Expressiveness of grammatical models appears to change the syntactic structures when comparing them with neutral designs. Expressive and neutral sentences, which are basic for them.

In colloquial English, the stylistic inversion is realized in the following models:

1. Inversion of a value expressed by an adjective which takes the final position in the sentence: *E.g. But it's a letter congratulatory!*

2. Adverb type inversion: *hardly, scarcely, no sooner, only, seldom, never*, particles of negative meaning, prepositions gives expression to the emotional color: *E.g. Never again, never again would he kill things (R. Aldington). Not only did he come but he stayed for a long time. Never could he understand me.*

3. Inversion of direct filling, which occupies the initial position: *E.g. Awful manners young Hopper has! (O. W. Plays).*

Especially here it should be noted and structures in combination with the words type *fine, good, swell, excellent, precious, lovely, likely, much*, which is preceded by an indeterminate or zero article. For example: *English a fine friend she turned out to be, the children I'm raising! , not only did he come but he stayed for a long time. Never could he understand me.*

Opponents of syntactic classification objections are convinced that the analysis of linguistic means of expressing objection should consider not only the syntactic features, but also morphological. Hence, offering classified objections, primarily in the English language in two principles:

- 1) morphological;
- 2) lexical and syntactic.

Morphological Classification of objections in modern English are realized through the following means:

- 1) negative particle: not;
- 2) negative adverbs: never, nowhere, no how, no whither, neither;
- 3) negative pronouns: no, none, nothing, nobody, naughty, neither;
- 4) negative conjunctions: nor, nor ... nor, neither, neither ... nor, less, unless;
- 5) Negative affixes: suffix - less; prefix un-, in- with its options as a result of assimilation dis-, non.

Lexico-syntactic classification is represented by such means as:

- 1) negative word-sentence;
- 2) phrase negation;
- 3) verbal negations.

Lexico-syntactic classification updates the relationship between a negative and affirmative values, including the emphasis on the opposition.

English language feature is that it odds-general objection can be expressed most the different members of a sentence, not just a verb-predicate. Negative sentences with the subject (nobody, nothing, none, no-one, etc.) are treated as general negation, despite the fact that they predicate their form is affirmative. This specific feature of British objections is relevant to the business of writing as one among functional styles of the English language. The researchers say that in English common objection does not have to be predicate; minor objections before the sentence could be partial and total (Shendels, 1979, p. 125). Thus, the difference between total and partial negation in English has no grammatical expression. In this regard of N. Bulakh notes that the lack of a clear grammar means for expressing partial denial of the latter in some cases indistinguishable from common objection without additional stylistic means, the most important of which are opposing affirmative (Bulakh, 1957, p. 244). According to his N. Bulakh characteristic indicator of general negative sentence is that it contains a negative pronoun or adverb (nobody, nothing, never, etc.) verb as it remains formally affirmative:

***Nothing** in this Article shall be deemed to impair the right of the master of a ship to require a seafarer to perform any hours of work necessary for the immediate safety of the ship, persons on board or cargo, or for the purpose of giving assistance to other ships or persons in distress at sea (Memorandum of agreement, 2014) (заперечний підмет *nothing*, формально стверджувальний присудок *shall be deemed to impair*);*

*It is understood and agreed that **nothing** contained in this Agreement is intended to or shall be construed as to restrict in any way the authority of the Master [www.sur.ru/mft/cont] (negative subject *nothing*, formally affirmative predicate *is intended to or shall be construed*).*

A similar way of expressing general denial in business English and typical designs of negative pronoun no:

***No** seafarer employed in the Deck or Engine departments who is 21 or over shall be paid less than the equivalent rate of an ordinary seaman (Memorandum of agreement, 2014).*

In this case the particle **no** objection relates directly to the subject, while the predicate shall be paid is formally affirmative:

*If **no** such vacancies exist, the lead teacher will be placed in the substitute pool in the district they served in as a lead teacher (Memorandum of agreement, 2014) (Subject negation no such vacancies, formal affirmative predicate exist).*

The next text fragment common objection is ensured through the use of a negative

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pronoun no adverbial group consisting of, but not the subject. This verb, as in the above text fragments, remains formally affirmative:

*In **no** event, however, shall the number of days worked in any school year under this work calendar be fewer than the number of days teachers would have worked had they reported, as before, on the Friday after Labor Day and worked through the last weekday in June (Memorandum of agreement, 2014).*

However, note that no share can also be used for the partial denial of the phenomenon, expressed noun or his substitute - the pronoun in the sentence in texts written business communication:

*If sufficient teachers do not choose a particular activity with any of their six choices, the Principal will assign teachers to these activities on a rotational basis in inverse seniority order with **no** teacher being involuntarily assigned to an administrative activity for consecutive years (Memorandum of agreement, 2014).*

As manifestations of partly negative meaning of pronoun no in English considers it appropriate to examine cases of its use as a part of cliché and widespread within the written business communication terms **no more (than)**, **no less (than)**, **no later (than)**, **no earlier (than)** , **no later (than)**:

*The hours of rest may be divided into **no more than** two periods, one of which shall be at least 6 hours in length, and the interval between consecutive periods of rest shall not exceed 14 hours (Memorandum of agreement, 2014);*

*The 37 minutes of the extended four (4) days per week shall be used for tutorials, test preparation and/or small group instruction and will have a teacher student ratio of **no more than** one to ten (Memorandum of agreement, 2014);*

*Each spring, but **no later than** April 15th, the principal shall meet to consult with the Chapter Leader on the number of positions for each menu item (Memorandum of agreement, 2014);*

*In single session schools, the day will start **no earlier** than 8:00am and end **no later** than 3:45pm.*

*Teachers identified as being at risk of being excessed at the commencement of the following school year will be informed of this **no later than** June 15, or as soon as is practicable if identified as being at risk of excess after June 15. The deadlines for excessing teachers will continue to be governed by applicable law (Memorandum of agreement, 2014).*

Objections at the site of action denies something that (to whom) directed the action. This element can be denied to the concept of the object, expressed noun. Given the peculiarities of the writing formal business-communication, the prioritized language level of the actual categorical reflection of the “denial” archaism and the individual expression of semantics in the material under study turned out to be grammatical.

The order is characterized by the desire of the speaker to force the listener to act and it is provided with the social role of the speaker-author of the order and his position in

relation to the listener. The objection is reaction to the speech act of the order. Consider the following examples:

For Immediate Release

November 15, 2010

Tea Party Leaders Release Letter Urging House and Senate GOP to Avoid Social Issues

(Washington, D.C.) – Today, a group of Tea Party leaders and activists released the following open letter to Rep. John Boehner (R-OH) and Sen. Mitch McConnell (R-KY). The letter urges Republicans in Congress to avoid social issues and focus instead on issues of economic freedom and individual liberty:

Dear Senator McConnell and Representative Boehner,

On behalf of limited government conservatives everywhere we write to urge you and your colleagues in Washington to put forward a legislative agenda in the next Congress that reflects the principles of the Tea Party movement.

Poll after poll confirms that the Tea Party's laser focus on issues of economic freedom and limited government resonated with the American people on Election Day. The Tea Party movement galvanized around a desire to return to constitutional government and against excessive spending, taxation and government intrusion into the lives of the American people.

The Tea Party movement is a non-partisan movement, focused on issues of economic freedom and limited government, and a movement that will be as vigilant with a Republican-controlled Congress as we were with a Democratic-controlled Congress.

This election was not a mandate for the Republican Party, nor was it a mandate to act on any social issue, nor should it be interpreted as a political blank check.

Already, there are Washington insiders and special interest groups that hope to co-opt the Tea Party's message and use it to push their own agenda – particularly as it relates to social issues. We are disappointed but not surprised by this development. We recognize the importance of values but believe strongly that those values should be taught by families and our houses of worship and not legislated from Washington, D.C.

We urge you to stay focused on the issues that got you and your colleagues elected and to resist the urge to run down any social issue rabbit holes in order to appease the special interests.

The Tea Party movement is not going away and we intend to continue to hold Washington accountable.

Sincerely,

Christopher R. Barron (Memorandum of agreement, 2014).

Traditionally, the denial particle **not** refers to grammatical means of expressing an objection, since, in its mediation, they form negative forms of auxiliary and main verbs. A. Pashlavskaya sees the peculiarity of modern English denial in the obligatory combination of particles with the auxiliary verb *do* in the analytic denial of the verb. In this case, in English, the particle is not a means of implementing the categorical value of the

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objection at the syntactic level. It can stand in different positions to the verb, forming a denial with it. For example: *The products of the territory of one Party imported into the territory of the other Party shall not be subject, directly or indirectly, to internal taxes or other internal charges of any kind in excess of those applied, directly or indirectly, to like domestic products. If sufficient teachers do not choose a particular activity with any of their six choices, the Principal will assign teachers to these activities on a rotational basis* (Memorandum of agreement, 2014).

Conclusions. Within the English and Ukrainian languages are numerous objections classification based on different criteria. These classifications reflect the attempts of scientists to systematize and specify objections phenomenon in language. The most common languages are in compared classification objections to the lexical and syntactic principles can be seen as a manifestation of typological affinity of these languages.

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